

Analysis of Land Surface Temperatures with Remote Sensing and Geographic Information Systems: The Case of Amasya City Center

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Abstract

Land surface temperature is defined as the radiative surface temperature of the ground surface. Climate change and global warming cause an increase in the surface temperature, unlike the atmospheric temperature. Remote sensing and geographic information systems are very important in issues such as the detection and analysis of surface temperatures. Remote sensing and geographic information systems were used to determine the surface temperatures in the city center of Amasya. From the Landsat-5-Landsat-8 satellite images, the surface temperature was analyzed as 10-year periods between 1984-2021. Accordingly, the surface temperatures have increased since 1984. The warmest year was 2021. As a result, the changes in the surface temperatures and the increase in the surface temperature affect the urban climate negatively by causing the cities to be more suffocating and hot. It is recommended to make ecological urban designs from a geographical point of view.

Keywords: Landsurface temperature (LST), Landsat-5-Landsat-8, Global warming, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Amasya

Yeryüzey Sıcaklıklarının Uzaktan Algılama ve Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemleri ile Analizi: Amasya Kent Merkezi Örneği

Öz

Yer yüzey sıcaklığı, yer yüzeyinin ışımsal yüzey sıcaklığı olarak tanımlanmaktadır. İklim değişikliği ve küresel ısınma atmosfer sıcaklığından farklı olarak yeryüzey sıcaklıklarının da artmasına sebep olmaktadır. Yeryüzey sıcaklıklarının tespiti ve analizi gibi konularda uzaktan algılama ve coğrafi bilgi sistemleri oldukça önemlidir. Amasya kent merkezinde yeryüzey sıcaklıklarının tespiti için uzaktan algılama ve coğrafi bilgi sistemleri kullanılmıştır. Landsat-5-Landsat-8 uydu görüntülerinden 1984-2021 yılları arası 10'ar yıllık dönemler olarak yeryüzey sıcaklığı analiz edilmiştir. Buna göre yeryüzey sıcaklıkları 1984 yılından itibaren artış göstermiştir. En sıcak yıl 2021 yılı olmuştur. Sonuç olarak yeryüzey sıcaklıklarında meydana gelen değişim ve yeryüzey sıcaklık artışı kentlerin daha bunaltıcı ve sıcak olmasına sebep olarak kent iklimini olumsuz yönde etkilemektedir. Coğrafi bakış açısıyla ekolojik kentsel tasarımların yapılması önerilmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yeryüzey sıcaklığı (LST), Landsat-5 ve 8, Küresel ısınma, Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemleri (GIS), Amasya.

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1. Introduction

The need for labor, which increased with the industrial revolution in the late 18th century, led to intense migration from rural to urban areas in the following periods. This situation has made the cities more crowded and suffocating day by day. Cities have different climatic conditions from the rural and semi-rural areas around them (Çağlak, 2022; Çağlak & Türkeş, 2022; Metin & Çağlak, 2022).

As the rate of urbanization increased, the use of natural resources and fossil fuels also increased. Increasing use of natural resources, increasing industrialization and urbanization have caused more greenhouse gases to accumulate in the atmosphere. Greenhouse gases accumulating in the atmosphere have triggered the warming of the Earth's climate by human influence. Climate is in a state of constant change throughout the history of the earth. However, anthropogenic effects have caused some changes on the world climate by affecting the rate of climate change. Global warming and climate change have different effects in different parts of the world. While heat waves and drought are effective in some places, extreme precipitation and cold waves are experienced in some places (Türkeş & Erat, 2017). In addition to such different effects of climate change on a world scale, it also causes similar effects throughout the world.

Globally, terrestrial glaciers are melting, underground and surface water resources are decreasing and surface temperatures are increasing (Abbas, Zhao & Wang, 2022). Land surface temperature is defined as the radiative surface temperature of the land surface. Surface temperature refers to different concepts with atmospheric temperature. While the surface temperature refers to the measurement of the heat reflected from the surface by means of satellites through thermal bands, the atmospheric temperature refers to the determination of the air temperature through the ground observation stations. Climate change and the accompanying global warming cause an increase in the surface temperature, unlike the atmospheric temperature. The increase in surface temperatures has negative effects on the ecosystem and living things. Changes in surface temperatures cause negative effects on many parameters such as the duration of snow on the ground, vegetation period of plants and soil moisture (Whan, Cheng, Hu & Liu, 2020). Changes in precipitation regimes in urban areas are also associated with changes in surface temperatures. In order for urban areas to be livable places by eliminating the negative effects of climate change, it is necessary to constantly monitor and monitor the urban environment conditions. Here, in parallel with the technological developments, geographical information systems and remote sensing techniques have gained great importance especially in recent years. The development of satellite technologies and the use of new satellites contribute to the development of remote sensing technologies. Remote sensing and geographic information systems techniques are frequently used in urban areas as well as in many areas. Welch (1980), after his work, started to use remote sensing techniques more in subjects such as the city and urban climate, surface temperature (Yüksel, 2006). Remote sensing and geographic information systems are very important, especially in subjects such as the detection and analysis of surface temperatures. Akyürek (2020), in his study, examined the relationships between land surface temperatures and urbanization, industrial activities and geothermal energy and stated that the land surface temperature differs in these areas.

Mercan (2020) stated in his study that urban areas are warmer than their surroundings and that the surfaces covered with vegetation have lower surface temperatures than other areas. The ability to calculate surface temperatures for large areas with the help of satellite images shows that these data can also be used in developed climate models (Şekertekin, Kutoğlu & Kaya, 2013). New tools and models have also been developed to calculate surface temperatures in a more practical way (Avdan & Kaplan, 2016). Studies have shown that surface temperatures and artificial areas are related (Balçık & Ergene, 2017). Many methods are used to calculate surface temperatures. Thermal and multi-spectral bands of different models and satellite images are used to calculate the surface temperature (Çelik & Kalkan 2012). In another study conducted in India, the correlation between surface temperature and spectral indices such as NDVI, NDBI, MNDVI, which were analyzed based on satellites, and the surface temperature were investigated (Pandey, Mondal, Kumay & Rasmi, 2022). Khurshid & Shirazi (2022), in their study in Pakistan, stated that there is a negative correlation between the land surface temperature and vegetation, and that the area covered by the vegetation

shrinks with the increase in land surface temperatures. Aryalekshmi, Mohammed, Biradar & Chandrasekar (2020) examined the relationship and difference between land surface temperatures and ground observation stations (meteorology stations) in their study in India and stated that there are differences in values between both types of observations. Pandey, Mondal, Guha, Upadhyay & Singh (2022) found in their study that as the urban area expands, the surface temperatures increase more. Maillard, Almonacid, Salazar & Alcazar (2023) state that deforestation increases the surface temperatures in their study in the Amazon basin in Bolivia. When we look at the literature, there are many domestic and foreign studies on the analysis of the surface temperature and the effect of different variables on the surface temperature or the possible effects of the surface temperature on different variables. This situation shows that the analysis of the land surface temperature with satellite images gives accurate and acceptable results. Therefore, the aim of the study is to analyze the changes in the land surface temperatures in the city center of Amasya, which is located in a narrow valley, and to reveal the reaction of the land surface temperatures to the changes in the urban area. Remote sensing and geographic information systems were used to determine the surface temperatures in the center. Accordingly, Landsat satellite images were used to analyze the temporal and spatial changes of land surface temperatures in the city center of Amasya. From the Landsat-5 and Landsat-8 satellite images, the land surface temperature was analyzed as 10-year periods between 1984-2021 using the same periods of the year.

2. Material and Method

2.1. Study Area

Amasya city center, which is located in the narrow and deep valley formed by the Yeşilirmak river as an antedant strait, was chosen as the study area. It is located on the southern slopes of the Canik Mountains in the Central Black Sea Section of the Amasya Black Sea Region, also known as the Black Sea Region. Amasya is adjacent to Tokat in the east, Çorum in the west, Samsun in the north and Yozgat in the south. The central district or city center of Amasya is a settlement established on the valley and foothills of Yeşilirmak, one of the largest rivers in Turkey (Figure 1). Yeşilirmak flows through the city of Amasya and divides the city into two. On the peripheries of the city center, high bare bedrock masses are found in blocks. Due to this feature, it is one of the most important settlement centers in historical processes. In the ancient period, it had a geostategic importance from the Pontus Kingdom to the time of the Ottoman Empire. It was even used as one of the centers where the princes received education due to its strategic location during the Ottoman Empire (Kuş, 2016).

Figure 1. Study area of location map.

According to the long annual climate averages of Amasya (1961-2021), the annual average temperature is 13.6 °C and the total annual precipitation is 460.2 mm. The highest temperature is

20.1 °C, the lowest is 8 °C (MGM). The climate of Amasya shows a transitional character between the Black Sea and the continental climate. In recent years, drought and its impact on water resources have affected Amasya as well as many cities of Turkey (Çağlak, Özlü & Şahin, 2017).

In the study, Landsat-5 and Landsat-8 OLI_TIRS satellite images were used to analyze the land surface temperatures (LST). Since it is the summer period in Turkey and the cloudiness of the atmosphere is lower, the month of August was chosen as the time for the study. 5 satellite images of the years 1984-2021 were used. Images from 1984 to 2021 at 10-year intervals from 1984, 1994, 2004, 2014 and 2021 were downloaded from the USGS Earth Data Explorer page. Since satellite images began to be obtained in the 1980s, the time interval of the study was chosen in this way. Band 4, Band 5, Band 6 and Band 11 thermal bands in the satellite images were used to analyze the surface temperature. Satellite images with a maximum cloud coverage of 10% and below were selected, and the parts within the range of path 175 row 032 covering the study area were used for LST analysis (Table 1).

Table 1. Satellite images and features used in the study

Satellite images	Properties
1984 Landsat_5	Path: 175, Row: 32 Date: 1984-08-31
1994 Landsat_5	Path: 175, Row: 32 Date: 1994-06-05
2004 Landsat_5	Path: 175, Row: 32 Date: 2004-08-31
2014 Landsat_8 OLI_TIRS	Path: 175, Row: 32 Date: 2014-08-31
2021 Landsat_8 OLI_TIRS	Path: 175, Row: 32 Date: 2021-06-07

There are formulas applied in several steps to calculate the surface temperature from satellite images (Sutariya, Hirapara & Tiwari, 2022). These formulas were calculated using Arcgis raster calculator. LST calculation steps for Landsat-5/7 and Landsat-8 satellite images include different processing steps.

2.2. Calculating Earth's Temperature from Landsat-5 Satellite Images

The values required to analyze the surface temperature are in the information file included in the satellite images. The surface temperature analysis made on the information file of Landsat-5 consists of three stages. First of all, the thermal band 6 used to calculate the surface temperature is opened in the Arcmap program and the calculation steps are carried out through the raster calculator tool. First, digital number(DN) convert to radiance (Şekertekin & Bonafoni, 2020).

$$L\lambda = (LMAX\lambda - LMIN\lambda) / (QCALMAX - QCALMIN) * (QCAL - QCALMIN) + LMIN\lambda \quad (1)$$

Where;

$L\lambda$ = Spectral radiance

QCAL = Quantized calibrated pixel value in DN

$LMAX\lambda$ = Spectral radiance scaled to QCALMAX in (Watts//m2 *sr*µm)

$LMIN\lambda$ = Spectral radiance scaled to QCALMIN in (Watts//m2 *sr*µm)

QCALMIN= Minimum quantized calibrated pixel value(corresponding to $LMIN\lambda$)in DN

QCALMAX= Maximum quantized calibrated pixel value(corresponding to $LMAX\lambda$)in DN=255

And then convert radiance into BT(brightness temperature) in Kelvin degree. Its using constant values to calculate IT (Table 2).

$$T = K2 / \ln(K1 / L\lambda + 1) \quad (2)$$

Where;

T= Effective at-satellite temperature in Kelvin

K2= Calibration constant 2

K1= Calibration constant 1

$L\lambda$ = Spectral radiance in (Watts//m2 *sr* μ m))

Table 2. Constant value table.

Sensor	Constant 1-K1 (Watts//m ² *sr* μ m)	Constant 2- K2 Kelvin
Landsat 7 ETM+	666.09	1282.71
Landsat 5 TM	607.76	1260.56
Landsat 4 TM	671.62	1284.30

2.3. Calculating Earth's Temperature from Landsat-8 Satellite Images

Calculation of land surface temperature (LST) with Landsat-8 is performed in 5 steps over Arcmap geographic information systems. Raster Calculator Tool is used for these analyzes. Many thermal bands are needed to obtain LST from Landsat-8 satellite images. While calculating LST with Landsat-8, NDVI analysis is also performed. NDVI is known as the Normalized Plant Difference Index. BAND-4 and BAND-5 among satellite images are used to calculate NDVI with Landsat-8. Landsat-8 surface temperature was analyzed using the following processing steps.

Digital number convert Top of Atmosphere (TOA) radiance. This means of, Using rescaling factor, Thermal Infra-Red Digital Numbers can be converted to TOA spectral radiance. For this, the following formula is used (Rajeshwari & Mani, 2014).

$$L\lambda = ML*Qcal+AL-Oi \quad (1)$$

$$L\lambda = 0.0003342*Band10+0.10000-0.29$$

Where;

$L\lambda$ = TOA spectral radince (Watts//m2 *sr* μ m))

ML= Radiance multiplicative Band (No.)

AL= Radiance Add Band (No.)

Qcal= Quantized and calibrated standard product pixel values(DN)

Qi= Correction value for band 10 is 0.29

Conversion to Top of Atmosphere Brightness Temperature(BT)

Spectral radiance data can be converted to top of atmosphere brightness temperature using the thermal constant values in Meta data file.

$$\text{Kelvin (oK) to Celsius (oC) Degrees BT} = K2/\ln (k1/ L\lambda+1)-273.15 \quad (2)$$

Where;

BT= Top of atmosphere brightness temperature (oC)

$L\lambda$ = TOA spectral radince (Watts//m2 *sr* μ m))

K1= K1 Constant Band (No.)

K2= K2 Constant Band (No.)

NDVI analysis is performed after Brightness Temperature conversion.

The Normalized Diffrential Vegetation Index(NDVI) is a standardized vegetation index which Calculated using Near Infra-red(Band 5) and red(Band 4) bands.

$$NDVI = (NIR - RED) / (NIR + RED) \quad (3)$$

Where;

RED= DN values from the RED band

NIR= DN values from Near- Infrared band

After performing NDVI analysis, Land Surface Emissivity(LSE) is the average emissivity of an element of the surface of the surface of the Earth calculated from NDVI values.

$$PV = ((NDVI-NDVI_{min}) / (NDVI_{max} - NDVI_{min}))^2$$

Where;

PV = Proportion of Vegetation

NDVI= DN values from NDVI Image

NDVI_{min} = Minimum DN values from NDVI Image

NDVI_{max}= Maximum Dn values from NDVI Image

$$E = 0.004 * PV + 0.986 \quad (4)$$

Where;

E = Land Surface Emissivity

PV= Proportion of Vegetation

0.986 corresponds to a correlation value of the equation

After these process steps, the surface temperature analysis is performed as the last step. The Land Surface Temperature(LST) is the radiative temperature which calculated using top of atmosphere brightness temperature, wavelength of emitted radiance, Land Surface Emissivity.

$$LST = BT / (1 + (\lambda * BT / c^2) * \ln(E)) \quad (5)$$

Here, $c^2 = 14388 \mu\text{m K}$

The values of λ for Landsat 8: for Band 10 is 10.8 and for Band 11 is 12.0

Where;

BT= Top of atmosphere brightness temperature($^{\circ}\text{C}$)

λ = Wavelength of emitted radiance

E = Land surface emissivity

$$C2 = h * c / s = 1.4388 * 10^{-2} \text{ mK} = 14388 \text{ mK}$$

h= Planck's Constant= $6.626 * 10^{-34} \text{ Js}$

s= Boltzmann constant= $1.38 * 10^{-23} \text{ JK}$

c= velocity of light= $2.998 * 10^8 \text{ m/s}$

As a result of the analysis of the equations described above with the Arcmap Raster Calculator tool, LST analysis was performed from Landsat-8 satellite images.

3. Findings and Discussion

It has been observed that there is a time-dependent change in the land surface temperatures obtained with the help of satellite images for the same period of the year, and this change is in the form of an increase in the land surface temperatures (LST) from past to present. In this study, which deals with the city center of Amasya, it was determined that the surface temperatures increased in the city center of Amasya and the surface temperatures were different at different points in the city. As a result of the surface temperature analysis made in Arcmap, the LST values are divided into several classes. Accordingly, the time-dependent change in temperature and color scale was analyzed.

In the LST map of 1984 in the city center of Amasya, the surface temperature was high in areas where urbanization is intense and settlement area is narrow. There is a difference between station measurements and surface temperature values. The surface temperatures in and around the Yeşilirmak river are lower than the artificial surfaces or the parts of the artificial surfaces far from the river. This situation shows the cooling effect of water surfaces and green areas in the city. In 1984, there were no areas shown in red where the surface temperature was extremely high. The surface temperatures have developed especially in a narrow area such as Şehirüstü Neighborhood, Yüzevler District, Kurşunlu District. LST is higher in areas with dense artificial surfaces. The places where LST values are low in the city center are the northern sections where the valley widens and the building density decreases (Figure 2). When other studies are examined, it is seen that there are similar situations.

Figure 2. 1984 year LST map

According to the 1994 LST map, there is an expansion in the area of earth surface temperatures. Temperatures around 21 °C -25 °C are only in a very narrow area where the river passes in August 1994. Temperatures around 30 °C are seen in the city walls. In the 10 years between 1984 and 1994, even though colder LST values are seen on the 1994 map, the area covered by the hot surfaces and the temperature values have increased compared to the 1984 snake. For this reason, although low LST values were observed locally in 1994, when the city center is considered in general, an increase in temperature is observed (Figure 3). Since the 1990s, urbanization and the amount of population living in cities have increased.

Figure 3. 1994 year LST map

In 2004, the change in surface temperatures continues in the direction of increase. The lower temperatures seen around the Yeşilirmak river in previous years are no longer seen in 2004. Surface temperatures with warmer values are dominant throughout the city. The high values of surface temperatures also increased in 2004 in terms of the area covered. In some parts of the city, LST values have taken much higher values than the surrounding areas, gaining the appearance of a heat island (Figure 4). The lowest value in the 2004 LST map is 25 °C. The lower temperature values seen in the previous year were not seen in 2004. Areas with low LST values lost their effect and became warmer here.

Figure 4. 2004 year LST map.

In 2014, LST values exceeded 35 °C in some parts of the city. The lowest LST value is 27 °C. Low temperature values, which were effective in previous years, are not seen in 2014. The parts shown with green color, which denotes low temperatures, have almost disappeared. Hot conditions also show their effect here. Red and its tones, which represent extremely hot conditions, have gained a more prominent appearance on the 2014 LST map. Especially around Hacilar Meydanı Neighborhood, which has been opened to more settlements in recent years, LST values increased in 2014 due to the increase in artificial surfaces. While the northern parts of the city and the valley, which were less populated in previous years, had low LST values, in 2014, they have higher surface temperature values compared to other periods due to the increased artificial surface area due to dense construction (Figure 5).

Figure 5. 2014 year LST map.

In the 2021 LST map, the city of Amasya is almost exclusively dark red and very dark orange. When it comes to 2021, the lowest temperatures in the city for the same period of the year start from 30 °C, and the highest temperatures sometimes exceed 38 °C in the city center. In 1984 - 1994, LST showed lower values around Yeşilirmak river. However, at the end of 37 years, even in these parts, the surface temperature values are above 35 °C (Figure 6). In today's climatic conditions, where climate change and global warming are effective, the rapid expansion of cities, the decrease in land and soil cover, the increase in building densities and the increase in concrete have affected the reflection properties of the ground and caused the LST values to increase.

Figure 6. 2021 year LST map.

Balçık & Ergene, 2017; Pandey, Mondal, Guha, Upadhyay & Singh, 2022; As in the studies of researchers such as Yüksel, 2006), the results of this study are similar to the literature. The increase in the presence of artificial areas due to the excess of urban land texture has led to an increase in land surface temperatures. Studies conducted both in Turkey and in the world show that the decrease in land use and especially urbanization and the presence of green areas cause an increase in the surface temperature of urban areas. In this study, it has been observed that the increase in urban area, especially in the unfavorable areas in terms of topography, the compression of the city increases the surface temperatures. It is revealed in studies conducted in many countries of the world that the surface temperatures increase with the effect of urbanization. Kwofie, Nyamekye, Boamah, Adjei, Arthur & Agyapong (2022) in their study in Ghana stated that the literature generally deals with LST increases in western developed countries, but urban growth causes LST increases even in relatively less urbanized areas such as Africa. Sumarmi, Mariza, Sari, Pratama & Tanjung (2022), in their study in Malang, the second largest city of Indonesia, stated that the increase in urbanization due to population growth causes an increase on the surface temperatures. This situation is similar to the findings of the study conducted in the city of Amasya, where the medium-sized urbanization process continues. Mita & Syahrani (2022), in their study, showed that LST values increased due to the increasing population density in the city of Tanjungpinang in the last 20 years, and a high correlation was found between population density and LST values. The fact that the LST values increased due to the urbanization of the city of Amasya from the past to the present gave results in parallel with other studies carried out in the world and Turkey.

4. Conclusion and Suggestions

According to the results of the study, the surface temperatures have increased since 1984 in the city center of Amasya. The warmest year was 2021. Changes and increases in surface temperatures cause cities to become more suffocating and hot, and by affecting the urban climate, it causes a change in the precipitation and temperature conditions of the cities. Changes in surface temperatures and the factors affecting the surface temperature are very diverse. Especially recently, increasing urbanization and artificial area pressure cause the surface temperature of cities to increase. It is thought that the rate of urbanization of cities cannot be reduced. This shows that cities will have increasingly higher LST values today and in the future. Rising LST values will cause negative effects on the natural and human texture of the city and will prevent cities from becoming livable areas. For this

reason, taking advantage of remote sensing and geographic information systems applications is important for urban climate and urban management plans.

In order to prevent or minimize these adverse conditions in cities, the amount of green spaces in urban areas should be increased. The amount of green areas should be distributed evenly throughout the city. Building density and heights, concreting and asphaltting levels should be reviewed. Urban parks, green buildings, water surfaces, etc. ecological planning is required. It is recommended to make ecological urban designs from a geographical point of view.

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The article complies with national and international research and publication ethics. Ethics Committee approval was not required for the study

Author Contribution and Conflict of Interest Disclosure Information

The article has a single author. There is no conflict of interest.

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